

×*Astroworthiopsis*: A New Nothogenus for Hybrids Between *Astroloba* and *Haworthiopsis* (Aloaceae)

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NEW TAXA PROPOSED HERE

×*Astroworthiopsis*

In 2013 Gordon Rowley elevated the *Haworthia* subgenus *Hexangularis* to generic status under the name *Haworthiopsis*. This necessitates a new nothogenus for hybrids between this genus and *Astroloba*.

×***Astroworthiopsis*** M.van der Meer **nothogen. nov.** = *Astroloba* Uitewaal × *Haworthiopsis* G.D.Rowley

Cumming (2014) lists seven cultivars that belong in this genus:

×***Astroworthiopsis*** ‘**Auriga**’ = *Astroloba herrei* Uitewaal × *Haworthiopsis scabra* (Haw.) G.D.Rowley = ×*Astroworthia* ‘Auriga’

×**Astroworthiopsis** ‘Fasher’ = *Astroloba herrei* Uitewaal ×
Haworthiopsis fasciata = ×*Astroworthia* ‘Fasher’

×**Astroworthiopsis** ‘Herat’ = *Astroloba herrei* Uitewaal ×
Haworthiopsis attenuata (Willd.) G.D.Rowley = ×*Astroworthia*
‘Herat’

×**Astroworthiopsis** ‘Hervis’ = *Astroloba herrei* Uitewaal ×
Haworthiopsis viscosa (L.) Gildenh. & Klopper = ×*Astroworthia*
‘Hervis’

×**Astroworthiopsis** ‘Herwart’ = *Astroloba herrei* Uitewaal ×
Haworthiopsis reinwardtii var. *brevicula* (G.G.Sm.) G.D.Rowley =
×*Astroworthia* ‘Herwart’

×**Astroworthiopsis** ‘Limerig’ = *Astroloba bullulata* (Jacq.)
Uitewaal × *Haworthiopsis limifolia* (Marloth) G.D.Rowley

×**Astroworthiopsis** ‘Monokeros’ = *Astroloba herrei* Uitewaal ×
(*Haworthiopsis sordida* (Haw.) G.D.Rowley × *Haworthiopsis* or
Haworthia sp.) = ×*Astroworthia* ‘Monoceros’ nom. instat. (ICNCP
Art. 21.11; ‘Monokeros’ is the Greek form of ‘Monoceros’).

LITERATURE

Cumming D. M. (2014). *Astroloba* Uitewaal: Inferred relationships from extensive hybridization. *Alsterworthia Int.* 14(2): 2-6.
